

AI Stimulations In Teaching Cell Division: A Case Study From Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic

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This study tends to investigate how AI-powered stimulated tools enhanced students' understanding of cell division. Using a quasi-experimental design of pre-test/post-test experimental/control groups. The study utilizes two (2) objectives, research questions, and a null hypothesis. Forty (40) students from Microbiology unit, Department of Basic and Applied Sciences at Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina State, Nigeria formed the population. Using simple random sampling by balloting, the participants were equally selected to form (n=20) each. Data was collected through a pre-test and post-test approach. Both groups underwent a pre-test using a researcher-made validated five simple questions (two-stage diagnostic test on cell division). The experimental group was then exposed to AI-stimulated learning, while the control group received conventional lecture method for a period of four (4) weeks. Data was then analyzed using Independent samples t-test and one-way ANOVA. The results showed a significant difference in post-test scores between the experimental and control groups, with a mean difference of 0.882 and statistical significance at $p \leq 0.05$. Findings of the study revealed that students who used AI-powered simulation tools showed higher post-test scores in understanding cell division compared to those who received traditional lectures. The study recommends integrating AI-powered technology-enhanced tools into biology practical aspects in science curricula to promote teaching and learning processes.

Keywords:
Understanding,
Teaching, Cell
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Stimulation tools

Introduction

The continuous growth of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has opened up new possibilities for improving instructional strategies in cell biology, especially for complex subjects like cell division (Makransky, Terkildsen, & Mayer, 2019). Despite its importance, cell division remains a challenging topic for students due to its complex and microscopic nature, which makes it hard to fully grasp (Mahto, 2024). These digital tools also support diverse learning styles by presenting content in both visual and auditory formats, thereby making abstract biological processes

easier to comprehend (Bonde et al., 2014). Given the variations in how students learn, AI-powered educational tools should be adapted to maximize student understanding and foster active engagement with the material.

Technology-enhanced learning tools powered by AI have changed how students learn difficult science topics. These tools use 3D models, interactive quizzes, and instant feedback to support different learning styles, such as visual or auditory learners. For example, students using AI animations often feel more confident in understanding processes like mitosis compared to just

reading textbooks. Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to the development of computer systems that can mimic human intelligence by learning, adapting, and improving performance through the use of algorithms and complex mathematical techniques (Mureşan, 2023). One of the major strengths of technology-based innovations in education is the ability to bring together multiple forms of media such as visuals, text, audio, and video into an engaging, interactive experience (Crozet al., 1999).

As schools and universities adjust to the evolving needs of students, artificial intelligence is becoming a powerful tool that can change traditional teaching methods and improve how students learn (Luckin et al., 2016). The use of online platforms has expanded educational opportunities by connecting a wide range of students and teachers. This shift to digital learning allows for more flexible and accessible education, encouraging many to engage with technology-based teaching methods (Redecker, 2017). In recent years, science education has moved away from simply memorizing facts and toward encouraging learners to develop a deeper, more meaningful understanding of scientific concepts. This shift calls for new teaching strategies and learning approaches, especially in complex fields like cell biology (DiCarlo, 2006)

The constant growth of scientific knowledge, combined with ongoing technological and societal shifts, has brought about a steady transformation in how education is delivered (Veselinovska, Gudeva, & Djokic, 2011). Studies on multiple representations suggest that teaching mitosis and meiosis through parallel visuals, supported by structured comparison prompts, enables students to better align

concepts and improve comprehension and retention (Mahto, 2024). With the use of interactive 3D models and animations, students may now see and engage with biological processes in real time, such as investigating cell structures, seeing processes like mitosis and meiosis, and comprehending molecular interactions.

Recent educational research conducted in Nigeria highlights the positive influence of technology-enhanced learning (TEL) on students' grasp of cell biology. For instance, a study by Idris (2024) investigated the use of a Computer Animation Learning Approach (CALA) among microbiology students at a polytechnic in Katsina State. Findings revealed that students exposed to the animated content showed a stronger understanding of cell biology topics when compared to peers taught through conventional methods. The use of 3D animations helped learners visualize internal cell structures and dynamic processes like cell division, making abstract concepts more concrete. Similarly, another study by Idris et al. (2024) in Nigerian secondary schools introduced students to multimedia animations focusing on “the cell as the basic unit of life.” Results indicated notable improvements in student motivation, comprehension, and the ability to retain information over time.

In a study conducted by Kalimuthu (2017), a pre-experimental research design involving a single group was used to assess the impact of animated instructional materials on student understanding of meiosis. Thirty-five tenth-grade learners participated in the study, completing both pre- and post-tests using the Meiosis Concept Test (MCT). The findings showed a marked improvement in post-test performance, suggesting that students developed a clearer

grasp of meiosis after the intervention. Analysis of the results further indicated that the animation-based teaching approach effectively addressed several prevalent misconceptions and significantly enhanced conceptual understanding of the topic.

In another recent investigation, Maborang et al. (2025) carried out a quantitative survey within a Private Catholic Educational Institution to explore the impact of artificial intelligence tools on student learning. The results revealed that incorporating AI technologies into the educational process led to noticeable improvements in learners' academic performance. The researchers noted that the presence of AI tools encouraged more meaningful engagement, increased student participation, and supported collaborative learning. Additionally, many students reported a positive attitude toward continued use of AI, recognizing its role in helping them overcome academic difficulties and boosting their overall learning experience.

Despite technological advancements, there remains a lack of studies exploring AI-enhanced learning of cell biology particularly in the context of teaching mitosis and meiosis within the study area. During the 2023/24 academic session, the researcher conducted a study using a mixed-method approach, which revealed that most students gained a solid understanding of the concept through the use of animated media packages. However, in the 2024/25 session, the same course on Applied Genetics (Plant breeding), was taught by the same lecturer. It was observed that many students struggled to recall foundational genetic concepts learned from their ND level, indicating a loss of prior knowledge. To bridge this gap, the present experimental research is aimed at investigating the impact of "Labster's Mitosis and Meiosis Virtual

Lab" (an AI powered-stimulated tool) targeting HND II Microbiology students in the Department of Basic and Applied Sciences, College of Science and Technology, Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Cell division is a fundamental aspect in cellular biology. The continuity of life mainly depends on cell division, which is responsible for the growth, development, and reproduction in living organisms. The process involves the complex phases and activities of mitosis and meiosis, which includes the prophase, metaphase, anaphase, and telophase, which are often difficult to visualize and understand due to their dynamic and microscopic nature. This poses significant challenges for students to comprehend. This complexity results in limited student's engagement, understanding, and retention of cell division concepts. Given the centrality of cell biology in all biology-related courses, there is a pressing need for teachers to leverage technology-enhanced learning tools, specifically AI-stimulated tools, to facilitate student comprehension of cell division. This challenges prompted the researcher to undertake a diverse studies in the study area with sole aim to bridges the research gaps.

Objectives of the Study

1. To assess how AI-powered stimulated tools enhanced students' understanding of cell division
2. To assess how technology-enhanced learning approaches improve students' retention of cell division concepts between the treatment and control groups

Research Questions

1. Is there a significant difference in the mean scores of students taught using AI-powered stimulated tools and those taught using traditional methods on the understanding and comprehension of cell division?
2. Do students exposed to technology-enhanced learning approaches have higher mean scores on the retention of cell division concepts than those in the control group?

Research Hypothesis

To answer the above research questions, one null hypothesis was stated at $p\text{-value} \leq 0.05$ to accept or reject it

HO1: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students' understanding, comprehension, and retention of the cell division concept when using AI tools in the treatment (AI-stimulated) as compared to the control (lecture method) group.

Methodology

This study employed a quasi-experimental pre-test/post-test research design to assess the effectiveness of AI-powered simulation tools in enhancing students' understanding, comprehension, and retention of cell division concepts. The population comprised 40 HND II Microbiology students from the Department of Basic and Applied Sciences at Hassan Usman Katsina Polytechnic, Katsina State, Nigeria. Participants were selected using a simple balloting method and randomly assigned into two equal groups: an experimental group ($n = 20$) and a control group ($n = 20$). Both the experimental and control groups were made up of students with

similar academic backgrounds, covering the same course content and learning level. The treatment period covers half of every lecture period/hour per week to be used for both groups separately.

Before starting the treatment, all participants took a pre-test using the Cell Division Two-Stage Diagnostic Test, which included short-answer questions as a treatment. After four weeks of teaching, the same test was given again as a post-test.

During the intervention, the experimental group used "Labster's Virtual Lab on Mitosis and Meiosis". This stimulation tool is a 3D animated multimedia interactive learning tool that explains each stage of cell division. This platform allowed students to watch how chromosomes behave, see the structure of cells, and repeat sections they didn't understand the first time. It also included quick quizzes and instant feedback to help students review what they learned and keep track of their progress. While the control group received traditional lecture-based instruction covering the same content and duration.

The data collected from the pre-and post-tests was analyzed using independent samples t-tests to compare the mean scores between the two groups and one-way ANOVA to assess the statistical significance of the observed differences. Statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS software.

Results

Research Question 1: Is there a significant difference between the mean scores of students taught using AI-powered stimulated tools and those taught using traditional methods to understand cell division?

Table 1: Result of t-test analysis obtained from data on of the sample

Pre-test	N	Mean	S.D	t-value	Sig.	Remark
Control	20	19.63	1.87	0.46	.000	Not Significant
Experimental	20	20.43	2.09			

Table 1 presents the pre-test mean scores for both the experimental and control groups. The analysis shows that the calculated t-value is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level. This means there was no meaningful difference between the two groups before the intervention.

Research Question 2: Do students exposed to technology-enhanced learning approaches have higher mean scores on retention of cell division concepts than those in the control group?

Table 2: The result of t-test analysis obtained from data of the sample

Post-test	N	Mean	S.D	t-value	Sig.	Remark
Control	20	52.46	13.28	14.38	.000	Significant
Experimental	20	92.81	5.31			

Table 2 presents the post-test results, showing a statistically significant difference between the two groups. The experimental group, which used the AI simulation tool, achieved a mean score of 92.81, while the control group, which received traditional lecture-based instruction, scored a much lower mean of 52.46. The calculated t-value of 14.38 confirms that this difference is highly significant at the 0.05 level. This finding indicates that the AI-powered simulation had a strong positive impact on

students' understanding of cell division. Students who engaged with the interactive virtual lab showed greater comprehension and retention of the topic compared to those taught through conventional methods.

Null Hypothesis (HO1): There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students' understanding, comprehension, and retention of cell division concepts when using AI tools (experimental group) compared with the lecture method (control group).

Table 3: One-Way ANOVA of Mean Scores on students' understanding, comprehension and retention

	N	Mean	SD	T	Sig. (2-t)	F	Sig.	Remark
Scores	40	0.882	1.54	93.52	0.001	9.98	.000	Significant

Table 3 presents the results of a one-way ANOVA test, which reveals a mean score of 0.882 with a standard deviation of 1.54. The analysis showed an F-value of 9.98 and a p-value of 0.000, indicating a statistically significant difference at the 0.05 level. Also,

the t-value of 93.52 and the Sig. (2-tailed) value of 0.001 confirm that the difference between the control and experimental groups is highly significant. The results confirmed a statistically significant difference between

the groups highlighting the efficacy of AI-powered simulations.

Discussion of Findings

The results from research question one revealed that there was no significant difference in the mean scores of students in their pre-test level before the administration of treatment; both the control and experimental groups showed a slight difference in their mean scores. Several studies support the findings of this research. This observation is consistent with the study by Gracy (2016), who investigated how blended learning impacted biology achievement among 100 senior secondary school students. The findings indicated that, prior to any instructional intervention, there was no statistically significant difference in biology performance between students exposed to blended learning and those taught using traditional methods. This suggests that both groups begin the study with relatively similar levels of understanding.

The results presented in Table 2 indicate a significant difference in the post-test scores, with the experimental group outperforming the control group. Similarly, Sangodoyin (2010) reported that targeted teaching interventions significantly enhance students' achievement in biology. Likewise, Telaumbanua (2025) emphasized in a literature review that artificial intelligence plays a vital role in simplifying the understanding of intricate biological processes. The study noted that AI-enabled platforms can deliver personalized learning experiences by adapting content to match individual learners' pace and comprehension levels. Additionally, these systems offer virtual lab environments that allow students to conduct experiments and engage in practical biology activities without the

limitations of physical laboratory infrastructure. Supporting this, Idris (2024) used a mixed-methods study involving 44 students and found that Technology-Enhanced Learning tools, such as computer animations, greatly improved understanding of cell biology concepts. These studies collectively highlight the growing role of AI-powered educational tools in improving biology education.

Results presented in Table 3 revealed a significant difference between the experimental and control group where the experimental group shows the effectiveness of AI stimulated tools enhanced teaching and learning cellular concepts. This is supported by Chen and Liu (2024) that students who taught an AI image-recognition robot using images related to cell division showed improved learning outcomes compared to those who learned through traditional lectures. This study offers valuable insights into how AI-powered learning tools can enhance students' grasp of cellular biology. Using a quasi-experimental design, it was demonstrated that students exposed to AI simulations performed better than those receiving conventional instruction.

Despite these results and findings, certain limitations were observed within the study; the relatively small sample size of 40 students may limit how well the findings can be applied to a wider student population. Also, the intervention lasted only four weeks, which may not be sufficient to assess the long-term impact of AI-assisted learning on students' retention and deep comprehension of biological concepts. The study was also restricted to a single topic cell division and conducted within just one academic institution, which may not reflect the effectiveness of the intervention across

various biology topics or different educational level.

To build on these findings, future research could involve a larger and more varied group of students, extend the study period to evaluate how well students retain what they've learned over time, and explore additional areas of biology beyond mitosis and meiosis. It would also be beneficial to examine how AI tools can be adapted to suit different learning preferences, with the goal of offering more personalized and effective learning experiences for diverse student groups.

Conclusion

In summary, the above findings confirm that: There was no significant difference between the experimental and control groups in their mean pre-test scores. This is important because it confirms that any differences observed in the post-test can be attributed to the intervention itself. There was a significant difference in the mean post-test scores in the experimental and control groups of students taught with AI-enhanced simulation tools as compared with the conventional lecture method. The result support the effectiveness of integrating technology-enhanced tools, particularly AI simulations, in improving academic outcomes in complex biology topics like mitosis and meiosis. There was a significant difference in the mean scores of the students in their understanding, comprehension, and retention of cell division concepts. This indicates that AI-stimulated tools promotes active learning and deepens conceptual understanding.

Recommendations

From the above findings, recommendations were made as follows:

1. Government at all level needs to invest in digital infrastructure and teacher

training. Through various stakeholders, the Ministry of Education should allocate resources for computer labs, reliable internet, and AI tools, incorporating technology-driven tools, particularly AI-stimulated tools into practical aspects.

2. Educational institutions need professional development for multimedia tools for their instruction. Seminars, workshops, and conferences on AI integration in education should be organized and attended by members.
3. Curriculum developers should embed interactive AI applications (multimedia packages, simulators and virtual laboratories) in biology courses. There is also a need to revise the curriculum to include technology-driven AI tools in the teaching and learning processes.
4. Therefore, there is a need for further researches on AI in science education. Future studies should explore a wider range of empirical and methodological gaps in the literature.

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